

Employees' Perceptions toward Job Rotation: Empirical Evidence from Sylhet, Bangladesh

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Abstract: The aim of this study is to investigate the employees' perceptions about job rotation among the employees of banking and non-banking financial institutions in the area of Sylhet, which is located in the north east region of Bangladesh. Job rotation is viewed as sequential job movements that are indispensable for skills, knowledge, behavior, as well as for career development. It reduces employees' monotony, stress, and in converse, it increases employees' productivity and helps them find their strengths and weaknesses regarding the job. Job rotation is considered a precious gem for the organization as well as employee development in the modern business arena. Two research objectives were set out in this motive. Those are (i) to identify and find out the reasons for job rotation and (ii) to measure the consequences of job rotation in the organization in that region. Moreover, this paper broadly covers the employee's viewpoint regarding job rotation from the viewpoint of reducing the monotony of the job, career planning, and development, creating the right employee-job fit, examining employee skills, competencies, and developing work experience. This paper will guide readers to understand how job rotation programs can influence an employee's productivity level, skills, experience, advanced learning, succession planning, and career development. The total number of respondents in the survey was 102. Among them, bank employees numbered 76 and non-banking financial institution (NBF) employees were 26. Qualitative and quantitative data have been used to analyze the data. Both primary and secondary data were collected for the purpose of completing this work. Primary data has been collected from the respondents through structured questionnaires. Secondary data also has been collected from review articles, journals, books, and different websites. Simple random sampling methods are used for data collection. The findings reflect that personalized job rotation programs are important for employees' career hankerings as they satisfy their needs for careers and lead to employee loyalty and commitment. It is also evident from the study that job rotation is related to positive employee attitudes, and high job rotation is involved with high levels of performance. Moreover, job rotation ensures employees' advanced learning and helps them prepare to embrace future challenges that might come from the business environment.

Keywords: Job rotation, Career development, Organizational development, Employee's performance.

1. Introduction

This paper examines different factors that stimulate employees' perceptions regarding job rotation programs. Various analyzing tools were used to identify the employee's viewpoint on job rotation programs. This work will show readers how job rotation works to reduce stress, minimize mental pressure, create enthusiasm, build interpersonal relationships with co-workers, increase employees' efficiency in learning, and provide an opportunity to develop skills in a variety of changing jobs. In addition, this paper also helps the readers to understand how job rotation detects employees' job-related strengths and weaknesses, develop work experience and how it works to broaden employees' knowledge skills, improve their planning and

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organizing skills, and receive advanced learning, etc.

Job rotation has great significance to organizational as well as employee development and it works for human resource development intrinsically. Bennett (2003) addressed that job rotation is a planned replacement of employees among various jobs within the same department in a particular organization. Job rotation is a dynamic and never-ending process. Krasman (2012) found that rotation does not change the basic nature of the jobs. Through job rotation employees can showcase a variety of their skills and it also an intrinsic motivation. Moreover, indeed.com (2021) explained that the purpose of job rotation is to make workers flexible and it involves moving employees to a new role in the same organization. Malinski (2002) suggested that motivated and satisfied employees can view rotation programs as career advancement paths while demotivated and dissatisfied employees express negativity on it. In addition, Baro (2012) reported that job rotation is an internal business partner or program to achieve the intention of job designing. A job rotation program helps to minimize the increased cost of employee absenteeism and turnover.

Job rotation has an obvious link to employee productivity. Delpasand *et al.* (2010) mentioned that job rotation has been found to release employees' boredom, monotony, stress level, and enhance job-related know-how. Besides, Melamed *et al.* (1995) revealed that repetition of work sometimes increases employees' boredom and where boredom exists, deviant behavior and job attitude will go undergo. Ellis (1999) suggested that job tenure has a negative relation to absenteeism and turnover and in converse positive relation with productivity, flexibility, and job satisfaction. Fægri *et al.* (2010) cited that job rotation up brings employees' problem-solving skills, multitasking, and job-related flexibility that increase the company's competitive advantage. Job rotation has several financial benefits to organizations. Rotation is the process of developing social and individual human capital. Literature by Noe (2010) suggested that rotation increases employees' sight on customer and brand loyalty, corporate culture, management philosophy, and also proliferates employees' skills, knowledge, and job-related abilities. Above all, Kaymaz (2010) addressed that shortage of employees or sudden increase of demand, job rotation programs may rescue organizations from difficulties by using employee's skills that they increased through rotation programs. Implementation of job rotation programs also has a few challenges. Sometimes job rotation may reduce employees' productivity and loss of their specialized skills. Blakely (2017) reported that rotation might not be fit for some industries as well as a few organizations and many times rotation can costly and time-consuming. Moreover, organizations need to be more cunny and intelligent at the time of implementing job rotation programs.

2. Literature review

Huang (1999) mentioned that job rotation encompasses a substantial impact on the organization and employees' productivity. Job rotation, very often it is called cross-training and it is a vital form of on-the-job training. In addition, Saravani *et al.* (2013) noted that job rotation might be exercised for the development of employees' knowledge, skills. And, when this strategy takes effect people who have rotated are predicted to master new knowledge and to integrate all facets of data resources within the organization. Literature suggests that job rotation is a linchpin activity for developing workers, and organizations as well as other HR functions, (Weichel *et al.* 2010). Job rotation is planned on-the-job training for cultivating future candidates of management by transferring a management trainee from one department to a distinct to increase his or her understanding and credentials in all told aspects, (Ho *et al.* 2009). Moreover, Coughlin (2018) narrated that in task rotation strategies, employees will move from task to task after a considerable amount of time or once the desired goal has been achieved.

Arya *et al.* (2004) identified job rotation as a method of voiding the ratchet effect. Tarus (2014) found that job rotation flourishes employees psychological and physical health via creating positive attitudes on employees, facilitating good health by reducing stress and increasing the range of employees through reduction of boredom to work, seeing things during a replacement perspective, decreasing in physically demanding portfolios and having self-motivation towards their positions in organizations. Arya *et al.* (2004) mentioned that job rotation can mitigate employee's monotony by providing task variety,

enhancing socialization, assisting in the management and executive development, and ameliorating the consequences of career plateaus. Coşgel *et al.* (1999) mentioned that job rotation is substantial to cater to the preferences of workers for a spread of tasks. Juneja (2017) addressed the objectives of job rotation are (i) reducing the monotony of the duty (ii) succession planning (iii) creating right-employee job fit (iv) exposing workers to any or all verticals of the corporate (v) testing employee skills and competencies, and (vi) developing a wider range of experience. Mohsan *et al.* (2012) found that rotation programs are not elegant, but necessary in today's professional climate.

Through job rotation employees expand their knowledge and improve productivity. Al-Nashmi *et al.* (2015) identified job rotation could be a very effective tool to empower employees and develop their horizons. Literature by Oparanma *et al.* (2015) suggested that job rotation involves the horizontal loading of the employees' tasks. Muneer *et al.* (2017) reported that most of the organization's inscription future challenges are tending to rent staff to implement different sorts of tasks efficiently. It's expected that by enlarging the task, the worker is going to be motivated. Oparanma *et al.* (2015) found that there are four major ways to enlarge employment viz: (1) Challenging the worker, asking employees to figure up to their potentials. (2) Replacing relatively difficult, repetitive, and boring tasks with machines and equipment's where possible to bolster efficiency. (3) Assigning more tasks or operations to the task. This can less monotony and more variety. (4) Using job rotation to permit the worker to find out new skills and to interact in a very style of task.

Dhanraj *et al.* (2014) narrated that job rotation programs are designed to process employees to change workstations at set intervals in an effort to scale back their exposure to risk factors related to Repetition Strain Injuries (RSI). Oluwatuase *et al.* (2019) mentioned that rotation liberates exhaustion resulting from the repetition of a task by changing jobs/tasks and reduces exposure to strenuous jobs. Campion *et al.* (1994) cited that rotation refers to any change in work assignment, usually indicated by a change in title or department that doesn't involve a change in compensation level. Thus, promotion may have many of the identical effects on career development as rotation, but we use rotation here to discuss job changes that don't seem to be the results of promotions.

Research by Gannon *et al.* (1971) indicated that job rotation is related to positive employee attitudes, and high job rotation is involved with obvious employee attitudes and high levels of performance. In addition, Ho *et al.* (2009) reported that job rotation should be greatly pragmatic in order that proliferate employees' performance. High frequency of job rotation might not be better; factors like employee background, skills, knowledge, learning status, and job familiarity should be taken into consideration for the frequency of job rotation. Employee or executive development literature suggests that rotation could also be associated with career development because it increases the experience. Campion *et al.* (1994) identified rotation has also been discussed within the context of developing managers or professionals into generalists. Muneer *et al.* (2017) revealed that using the job rotation tool, the inspiration of the talent grows, and employees can move from strength to strength, creating a winning situation for you and therefore the company.

Job rotation reduces employees' social loafing activities. Eriksson & Ortega (2006) stated that social loafing is defined as individuals intentionally exerting their efforts when they work in a group. Job rotation can change employees' attitudes toward interpersonal relations and communication. In modern business organizations personalized job rotation programs by asking targeted employees about their career hankering as so to satisfy their needs for career, have a more loyal and committed workforce. Mohsan *et al.* (2012) cited that it is believed and strategically proved that loyal and satisfied employees can lead the company toward its intended goal and help to achieve a competitive advantage. Coşgel *et al.* (1999) identified there are practices apart from job rotation that also broaden the degree of specialization of workers. The rotation has been viewed as an

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environmental deftness for career development. Campion *et al.* (1994) addressed that sequential job movements are indispensable for skills, knowledge, behavior, and for career development.

3. Objective

The aim of this study is to investigate the employees' perceptions about job rotation among the employees of banking and non-banking financial institutions. This motive includes two specific research objectives.

- a) To identify and find out the factors that instigate employees' acceptance of job rotation and
- b) To measure the consequences of job rotation in organizational development.

4. Research Questions

The main research questions of this study are-

- a) How do job rotation programs reduce employees' monotony and work stress?
- b) How can rotation programs contribute to individual and organizational development?
- c) Does job rotation brush up employees' skills, competencies, and work experience?
- d) What are the contributions of rotation programs to employees' career planning and development, and creating the right employee-job fit?

5. Research Methodology

5.1 Research type

The study is empirical research in nature. This study mainly followed quantitative and qualitative research approaches for data collection and analysis. Qualitative data has been used for developing the conceptual framework and quantitative data has helped to understand the factual scenario. The theoretical background sets the stage for numerical analysis. Research data was collected through the use of structured questionnaires (Juneja, 2019).

5.2 Research design and data analysis tools

The data and information required for the study were collected from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data has been collected from the respondents through a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was suitably designed and self-administered. In the structured questionnaires, multiple-choice questions are used to collect demographic and other data. The five-point Likert scale was used to obtain data and it varied from 1 = 'Strongly disagree' to 5 = 'Strongly agree'. The secondary data was collected from published materials such as journals, books, articles, websites, and computerized databases for literature review. This paper covered a total of 25 statements under the five broad variables. To input the data and carry out the required analysis on it, SPSS version 22.0 and MS Excel has been used.

5.3 Participants

The population mainly included all male, female, and LGBTQ employees in the banking and non-banking sectors of Bangladesh. The sample frame involves bank and non-banking finance (NBF) employees from Sylhet, Bangladesh, which is located in the northeast region of Bangladesh. A total of 102 respondents were surveyed through structured questionnaires. Among them, 77 and 25 were from banks and non-banking financial institutions respectively. No LGBTQ employees were found to circulate questionnaires. The total number of male and female respondents was 77 (75.5%) and 25 (24.5%) respectively. The data was collected with the help of a simple random sampling method.

6. Data Analysis and Discussion

Demographic data was collected through the use of a questionnaire. For the purpose of the analysis, the sample size taken is of 102 respondents and all of them are valid. 75.5 % of the participants in this study were male, and 24.5% were female.

Table 1: Gender of Respondents

		Gender of Respondents	Age of Respondents
N	Valid	102	102
	Missing	0	0

Table 2: Frequency Table of the Gender of Respondents

Gender of Respondents					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	77	75.5	75.5	75.5
	Female	25	24.5	24.5	100.0
	Total	102	100.0	100.0	

Table 3: Age of Respondents

Age of Respondents					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than 30 years	17	16.7	16.7	16.7
	30 - 35 years	42	41.2	41.2	57.8
	36 - 40 years	18	17.6	17.6	75.5
	41 - 45 years	21	20.6	20.6	96.1
	More than 45 years	4	3.9	3.9	100.0
	Total	102	100.0	100.0	

Factor analysis and dimension reduction were used to analyze the data. The factor analysis uses the Principal Component Analysis method to extract the factors with the varimax rotation technique. Two widely used measures enable us to ascertain whether factor analysis is appropriate for the study namely Bartlett's test of sphericity ($p < .05$), and the KMO index within a range of 0 to 1, with a minimum value of .6 (Tabachnick *et al.*, 2007).

Table 4: KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.784
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	974.007
	Df	300
	Sig.	.000

From the above table, it is evident that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy in this study was at .784 and which mean was at .000 that factor analysis is appropriate for this study.

Factors with an eigen value of 1.0 or more are to be retained for further analysis. In our study, seven components scored an eigen value of 1.0 or more.

The key output of principal component analysis is the rotated component matrix, which contains the correlations between each of the variables and the estimated components. This study's sampling adequacy for each variable has a good correlation. The rotated component matrix represents the items with loadings above .4. In this study, seven components represent 15.89, 9.56, 8.82, 8.29, 7.83, 7.54, and 5.80 percent of the variance.

Table 5: Rotated Component Matrix^a

Rotated Component Matrix ^a							
	Component						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
The Job rotation program helps to brush up my level of expertise	.831						
Does job rotation help to broaden employee's knowledge skills	.715						
I do believe job rotation can increase employees' productivity	.703						
Job rotation programs improve my planning and organizing skills	.694		.403				
Effective job rotation programs can prepare employees to take future challenges	.684						
I have gained a lot of experience through job rotation	.558	.418					
Knowledge gained through job rotation has influence to my job evaluation	.476						
Job rotation programs are designed to create future leaders (succession planning).	.459			.412			
Job rotation gives the opportunity to develop skills in a variety of changing jobs		.772					
Job rotation programs able to detect employee's job related strengths and weaknesses		.664					.423
Job rotation programs help to know whole as well as intra-departmental culture		.598					
Job rotation can converse and engage with co-workers		.471					
Management gets to know more about the employee			.821				
Job rotation creates a pave/path to receive advanced learning			.586				
Job rotation is a tool for career development that will lead to promotion			.567				
Through Job rotation, employees get the best insight about management philosophy and culture			.468				
Job rotation helps to find the right person for the right position				.745			
I believe that job rotation programs can enhance my job stability				.697			
Job rotation gives the actual roadmap to achieve career planning				.665			
Job rotation programs help to minimizing mental stress					.791		
Job rotation reduces the boredom of employee's work					.721		
Working with a new manager is exciting and leads productivity					.520		
Gathering new knowledge and skills are always create enthusiasm					.486	.471	
Job rotation helps to increase employee's efficiency in learning						.758	
Job rotation programs may uncover the employee's hidden potentials							.779
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.							
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.							
a. Rotation converged in 9 iterations.							

The study determined seven main factors extracted from factor analysis:

Factor 1: From the results listed above it is evident that the first component consists of eight items one of which corresponds to employee-job fit, four of which relate to employee skills and competencies, and the rest of the three items are related to developing work experience. It includes items such as job rotation programs that help brush up employee's level of expertise, broaden employee's knowledge skills, increase employees' productivity, improve employee's planning and organizing skills, and prepare employees to take future challenges by gaining experience through job rotation. Knowledge gained through job rotation has an influence on job evaluation, and job rotation programs are designed to create future leaders (succession planning).

Factor 2: The second component consists of five items, where one item corresponds to each variable. Employees believed that they gained a lot of experience through job rotation, developed skills in a variety of changing jobs, detected employees' job-related strengths and weaknesses, helped to understand the whole as well as intra-departmental culture, and conversed and engaged with co-workers.

Factor 3: The third component contains five items one of which corresponds to career planning and development, one with employee-job fit, and one with employee skills and competencies. The rest of the two items are related to developing work experience. These items are related to improving employees' planning and organizing skills, management getting to know more about the employee, creating a path to receive advanced learning, using it a tool for career development that will lead to promotion, and employees getting the best insight about management philosophy and culture.

Factor 4: The fourth component involves four items two of which are consistent with employee-job fit, and the other two are relating to career planning and development. Job rotation programs are designed to create future leaders (succession planning), as well as help to find the right person for the right position. Moreover, employees believed that job rotation programs could enhance their job stability, and job rotation gives the actual roadmap to achieve career planning.

Factor 5: The fifth component comprises four items all of which correspond to reducing the monotony of the job. Job rotation programs help to minimize employees' mental stress and reduce the boredom of their work. They believe that working with a new manager is exciting and leads to productivity, and gathering new knowledge and skills always creates enthusiasm.

Factor 6: The sixth component entails 2 items one of which matching to career planning and development, and the other one is corresponding to reducing the monotony of the job. Gathering new knowledge and skills are always creating enthusiasm among employees, and helps to increase employee's efficiency in learning

Factor 7: The seventh component consists of two items, both of which conform to employee-job fit. Job rotation helps to increase employees' efficiency in learning and may uncover the employee's hidden potential.

7. Findings of the study

Based on the above-mentioned results and discussions, we can sum up our study through the following-

Gaining experience through job rotation is much more important to the employees as it resides in both the first and second components. The highest positive individual loading (.831) the respondents placed on the item "The Job rotation program helps to brush up my level of expertise".

Job rotation programs improve employees' planning and organizing skills and also work to gather new experience. Our study identified both items as mutually inclusive with factors 1 and 3 and 1 and 2 respectively.

In this study, we found similar results to Tarus (2014), who mentioned that job rotation programs actually work to reduce work-related boredom, stress, and conversely develop productivity and identify career-related skills gaps that are also addressed in another research work.

This study found that job rotation has strong relations with developing future leaders and helps to identify employees' strengths and weaknesses. In factor analysis, we observed both variables were found mutually inclusive with factors 1 and 4, and 2 and 6 respectively.

Saravani *et al.* (2013) noted that job rotation might be exercised for the development of employees' knowledge and skills. And we found these items in factor 1 with the loading of .694 & .403 (mutually inclusive with factors 1 and 2) and factor 2 with the loading of .772. In our study, we have found that factor 1 covers the highest number (8) of variables that indicated the job rotation has strong ties with them. These are job rotation brush up employees' expertise, broadening workers' knowledge and skills, productivity, planning, and organizing skills, preparing employees to take future challenges, proliferating experience, influence on job evaluation, and also for succession planning.

Job rotation programs are an important tool for employers to analyze individual employees. In our analysis, it is found that the second-highest loading .821 indicated management getting to know more about the employees through the job rotation program. Our findings have a sound link up with Noe (2010), who prescribed job rotation has many financial benefits and it is through developing employees' human capital such as skills, knowledge, and job-related psychological and physical abilities that we have seen in factor 1 with the loading of .715.

8. Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, multiple recommendations have been made-

- a) Job rotation would not be very effective for all departments in a particular organization. Some manufacturing organizations need a few or every department specialized skilled employees with detailed knowledge of every process. So, the tailoring approach could be used in this respect.
- b) The objectives and purposes of job rotation need to be clear and well-defined. Proper job analysis is important before initiating and designing job rotation programs for targeted employees.
- c) Employees may experience stress and anxiety as a result of job rotation if they are the wrong choice. Identifying the right person for the right rotational work is recommended.
- d) The organization should be more cautious at the time of designing employee rotation programs. Effective rotation programs can help to improve employees organizing and planning skills and also help to create future leaders.
- e) Organizations should carefully select competent workers for the effectiveness of rotation programs. Many times, employees do not get insight into the rotation program and management philosophy. Our research indicated that the lowest individual loading was .468 (not mutually inclusive).
- f) Identify the potential candidates and train them before shifting to the new department. Discover who has minimum basic skills for forthcoming departmental work. Otherwise, rotation programs may fail to lead to the intended results.
- g) Carefully monitor the performance of every employee' movement and their work results,, which might affect employees as well as organizational productivity.
- h) Organizations should be more concerned about developing employees' basic skills that may increase their enthusiasm.

9. Conclusion

In a nutshell, this study provides good insight into the relationship between job rotation and organizational as well as employee development. Our study has found a few components have a high impact on rotation programs, such as it brushes up employees' expertise, broaden workers' knowledge and skills, productivity, career development, preparing employees to take future challenges, and proliferating experience. In contrast, a few have a low impact, such as getting the insight of management philosophy and building relations with co-workers, but among them, none of the factors are deniable. Campion et al. (1994) addressed that sequential job movements are indispensable for skills, knowledge, behavior, and for career development. The organization must show maximum efficiency at the time of designing and implementing job rotation programs. Effective rotation programs can lead to a competitive advantage for long-term business survivability.

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Appendix:

Table 6: Total Variance Explained

Total Variance Explained									
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	6.984	27.935	27.935	6.984	27.935	27.935	3.974	15.894	15.894
2	2.441	9.765	37.700	2.441	9.765	37.700	2.392	9.567	25.461
3	1.599	6.397	44.097	1.599	6.397	44.097	2.205	8.821	34.282
4	1.456	5.824	49.921	1.456	5.824	49.921	2.074	8.296	42.578
5	1.247	4.986	54.907	1.247	4.986	54.907	1.959	7.836	50.415
6	1.145	4.582	59.489	1.145	4.582	59.489	1.894	7.574	57.989
7	1.076	4.304	63.793	1.076	4.304	63.793	1.451	5.804	63.793
8	.963	3.853	67.647						
9	.882	3.528	71.174						
10	.817	3.268	74.442						
11	.769	3.076	77.519						
12	.680	2.721	80.240						
13	.670	2.681	82.921						
14	.568	2.270	85.191						
15	.532	2.128	87.320						
16	.493	1.971	89.290						
17	.460	1.839	91.130						
18	.404	1.615	92.745						
19	.361	1.444	94.189						
20	.325	1.299	95.488						
21	.288	1.152	96.640						
22	.263	1.052	97.693						
23	.232	.929	98.621						
24	.193	.774	99.395						
25	.151	.605	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Figure 1: Screen Plot